

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF CHILD REARING IN THE FAMILY.

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Annotation: *This article discusses the methods used to activate foster children in preschools and in the role of family role.*

Keywords: *Preschool education, innovative technology, method, lesson, teaching method, interactive education, collaboration, parent, family.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida va oilaning o'rni hamkorligi jarayonida tarbiyalanuvchilarni faollashtirish uchun foydalaniladigan metodlar haqida fikrlar bildirilgan.*

Tayanch iboralar: *Maktabgacha ta'lim, innovatsion texnologiya, metod, dars, o'qitish metodi, interfaol ta'lim, hamkorlik, ota-ona, oila.*

In recent years, improving the quality and efficiency of the education system in the country, the formation of modern knowledge and skills of preschoolers, close cooperation and integration between the education system and science, Systematic work is underway to ensure its continuity and continuity. At the same time, the current state of the national education system requires its modernization in accordance with modern requirements, the education of young people as highly educated, physically and spiritually healthy people, the prestige of leaders and teachers of educational institutions. increase, requires the implementation of consistent measures to create the necessary conditions for their effective operation.

Historically, the great Greek scholar Aristotle said, The fate of the homeland is decided by the upbringing of young people. This means that the issue of education and upbringing has always been relevant since the beginning of human life. The role and importance of the pre-school education system in the life of our society, which

is the most important link in the upbringing of our children, cannot be measured by anything. It is the focus on pre-school education that will lay a solid foundation for the country's future development.

Preschool education is a rich national culture of children Mental and spiritual upbringing of children on the basis of historical heritage and universal values. promotes the development of thinking. As a result, a new ministry was established. Development and implementation of a unified state policy in the field of preschool education under the new ministry Expanding the state and non-governmental network of preschool education and strengthening the material and technical base, providing them with qualified teaching staff, covering children in preschool education The tasks are set to radically improve the quality of comprehensive intellectual, spiritual-aesthetic, physical development of children and their preparation for school through the sharp increase in education, the introduction of modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process.

Today, a state program on expanding the network of preschool educational institutions, strengthening their material and technical base, construction of new kindergartens has been adopted and is being implemented. Taking into account the experience of developed countries, great attention is paid to the expansion of the network of non-governmental educational institutions, including non-governmental kindergartens. Forms of cooperation with parents in preschool education are important to ensure the full development of the child. The above evidence shows that one of the most important issues is the formation of parents' perceptions of the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality. the need to develop, develop, implement and put into practice. Indeed, educational reforms have greatly contributed to the emergence of a certain level of human intellectual potential, its place in society. Therefore, the principles of the state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan state that the role of adults in the education and development of children is fundamental and important. This shows that the cooperation of adults,

especially parents and educators, is very important for the overall healthy development of the child.

Observations show that some of the shortcomings are that parental cooperation of preschoolers is not up to standard. This is due to the fact that there are enough teaching aids and conditions in preschool education and secondly, the lack of knowledge among educators in organizing activities with parents. The Concept of Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 provides for the elimination of problems in the field and the provision of quality preparation of preschool children for school education. That is why we chose the topic Formation of positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality of parents. The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "Expanding the network of preschool educational institutions and radically improving the conditions for the full intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children in these institutions, and providing access to them, improving the skills of teachers and professionals." This, in turn, includes the integration of modern approaches to the integrated content of preschool education, the identification of pedagogical and psychological directions to ensure children's intellectual activity, the identification of methodological opportunities for developing children's thinking in preschool education, the development of children's thinking. a model of a focused pedagogical process requires interaction between the preschool organization and the family, and development based on priority principles. Today, the attitude of parents towards preschool education remains negative.

The formation of a child's personality in preschool education is one of the most pressing issues in preschool education today. Based on the above considerations, it is important to form the perception of parents about the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality. In short, preschool is the beginning of lifelong learning. It helps the child to develop into a healthy and developed person, stimulates the desire to learn, prepares him for systematic learning. Therefore, it is necessary to further strengthen the system, study

the socio-philosophical, psychological, pedagogical and methodological sources, identify new areas of cooperation with the family in the formation of parents' perceptions of the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality. Development of scientific and methodological recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the formation of mothers' perceptions of the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality, the study of modern methods of preparing children for school education, the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of children's personality to determine the level of effectiveness of cooperation between family and preschool education organizations in the formation of perceptions, to carry out pedagogical practice on the basis of research results One of the most pressing issues of today's preschool education organization is to increase and create a methodological development based on the results. That is why I think it is important to form positive aspects of the organization of preschool education in the formation of the child's personality.

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